

THE ROLE OF INNOVATION AND USE OF TECHNOLOGIES IN LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Annotation: This work explores the significant impact of innovative practices and modern technologies on the acquisition of foreign languages. It discusses various technological tools, such as language learning apps, online platforms, and interactive multimedia resources, that enhance engagement and facilitate personalized learning experiences. The text emphasizes the importance of integrating these technologies into traditional language education, highlighting how they cater to diverse learning styles and promote self-directed learning. Additionally, the study examines case studies showcasing successful implementations of technology in language learning environments, illustrating the transformative potential of innovation in enhancing linguistic skills, cultural understanding, and overall learner motivation.

Аннотация: В данной работе исследуется значительное влияние инновационных практик и современных технологий на овладение иностранными языками. В нем обсуждаются различные технологические инструменты, такие как приложения для изучения языков, онлайн-платформы и интерактивные мультимедийные ресурсы, которые повышают вовлеченность и облегчают персонализированное обучение. В тексте подчеркивается важность интеграции этих технологий в традиционное языковое образование, подчеркивая, как они удовлетворяют различные стили обучения и способствуют самостоятельному обучению. Кроме того, в исследовании рассматриваются тематические исследования, демонстрирующие успешное внедрение технологий в среду изучения языка, иллюстрирующие преобразующий потенциал инноваций в улучшении языковых навыков, культурного понимания и общей мотивации учащихся.

Key words: skill, development, technology, innovation, creative thinking, multimedia resources, implementation, learning environment, interactive, online platforms, language learning apps

"The priority policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan is to democratize the work content of the educational system, to educate the youth of the 21st century

into comprehensively developed, mature, worldly-minded, educated, well-rounded individuals in accordance with the world education standards". The current issues of education and pedagogy include the purpose and essence of education, content, methods, as well as issues of scientific provision of the organization of the process based on the use of advanced modern technical achievements. Pedagogical technology has different characteristics depending on the content. Also, every pedagogue should organize the education and training process based on his competence and professional skills. It should improve the service of students and teachers in the implemented interactive lessons. It is necessary to increase the expectations of independent, free, logical and creative thinking in the student. Today, the science of pedagogy is reaching a certain level of development. There are certainly objective reasons for this.

Pedagogical approaches to the process of achieving the goal of education have also been different during socio-economic, scientific and technical development. So, as the goal of education and the process of its implementation improves from a theoretical and practical point of view, the science of pedagogy begins to become modern.

Today, our pedagogy does not tolerate such a situation. Education is a specially organized activity of pedagogues and students for regular and purposeful influence on the spiritual and physical condition of a person and the realization of educational goals in the pedagogical process. Technology is a set of methods of preparation, re-preparation of objects, materials, semi-finished products, changing the condition, properties, and shape of objects in the production process.

Pedagogical technology is a system of continuous interconnected actions of a pedagogue aimed at the planned and uniform implementation of a pre-planned pedagogical process in practice or solving a pedagogical problem; Secondly, it is a system of continuous, mutually conditioned actions of the pedagogue, which is related to the use of one or another set of education and training methods; Thirdly, a carefully developed and strictly scientifically designed pedagogical action that guarantees the achievements of the pedagogue; Fourthly, it is a systematic method of acquiring, creating, using and defining knowledge based on technology and human factors and their interaction, focused on the optimization of educational forms. , is a system for creating, analyzing and analyzing the entire learning and knowledge acquisition process. Regardless of the student's knowledge in this specialty, when entering the learning process, it is necessary to have the necessary pedagogical minimums,

which are the sum of pedagogical and psychological knowledge, technology and teaching methods.

At the same time, it is necessary to constantly develop the skills and abilities to implement innovative technologies aimed at increasing the effectiveness of education. There is one code in the science of adult education, that is, Andragogy. That is, a person, including a listener, can reach the highest level of professionalism only when he moves with his will. Most of the time, our employers consider their professional competence to be high and they still have a good reputation.

First of all, it is necessary to create trust in such listeners. Secondly, the internal and external motivation of listeners is not the same. These are the reasons why there are some problems in increasing the efficiency of the lesson. Factors that increase effectiveness of the lesson include pedagogical and managerial skills, organization ability, appropriate use of learning resources, and especially knowing how to allocate time properly and accurately.

Educational technologies are an imaginary use of modern information technology in the process of education. It also envisages increasing the quality and efficiency of education through importing modern innovative technologies in the educational process. Appliances, in the learning of the foreign language, have several benefits to the use of such information and communication technologies. The role of modern analysis in language learning and teaching is incomparable. The use of technological means comes to a foreign language in every aspect of learning (reading, lying, hearing, and speaking). For example, to hear, of course, this process without computer, player, CD discs cannot be done. Listen is one of the most important parts of language learning language. In this case, the student is required to follow the pronunciation at the same time, following grammatical rules, vocabulary and its meanings. In the educational process, students of students are also an important factor in the use of information - communication technology in the use of modern technologies. The teaching of a foreign language using modern technologies is one of the most effective ways. In this process,

Including:

- When using computers, the reader can also see a foreign language video roll range, protests, dialogue movies or cartoons;
- Listening to radio broadcasts and tv programs in english can be effecient in learning a foreign language.

- Use of tape recorder and cassettes, which is considered a much traditional method;
- CD players can be used. Using this technical means is more efficient and ensures to make the lesson be more interesting.

In the process of globalization, it is difficult to pursue our lives without internet. The most effective methods of learning a foreign language and the fruitful use of it during the process of teaching. The Internet will have the opportunity to communicate with foreign language speaking. You can improve the writing training exercise by correspondence via email.

The introduction of modern and communication technology in the educational process is the most important issue, using them, using them, and increasing their interest in the student through them. This is the opportunity to use the innovation technologies of education and increases.

Today, there are several different methods of innovation education technologies. From them, when wide and different methods are used to cover the topic in the lessons, the effectiveness of the lesson will be high and the increase in interest to classes of students. Improving the effectiveness of education through the implementation of the import and application of the professor to the educational process. The use of different roles, moving games even in training foreign language lessons will also increase interest in class to learn the language. Help to communicate in pairs or small groups of students to communicate with others gives.

In the educational process, in the coverage of the topic of graphic organizers, it is one of the most important visits to deliver it to students. Using graphic organizers in teaching a foreign language, it is advisable to explain the grammatical rule on the theme. If they are given these, remain in mind will be easier.

The use of various tables in the process of teaching a foreign language is also beneficial. Using tables in the educational process, students can place a certain grammatical rule, such as the use of times, can post a new schedule. At a time when the need to learn a foreign language, in the educational process, in the educational process, in the field of modern information technology, innovation educational technologies. Effective use leads to the product effective process.

The most important factor that determines the effectiveness of the lesson is the formation of the purpose of the lesson. If the goal of the project is correct, specific, limited by time, and the possibilities of achieving the goal are real.

If the listener is skilled, he is considered to be skilled. In addition, conducting lessons in a combined way helps to make the lesson colorful and effective. A combined project is considered to be a combination of different types of projects and one type of interactive methods with another type, while providing coherence to the purpose of the project at the same time. For example, if the learner believes in his skills, he can combine the activity houses with the role-playing houses in the process of learning, or he can use the method of working in a small group at the same time with individual work based on the principles of cooperative learning in a lesson designed to acquire new knowledge. Interactive dare guarantees the quality of education. Because in the process of interactive education, the main task of the teacher is not to make the student sleep, but to manage the educational process and create conditions for the student. Since the problem is solved by the user, the user's connection is guaranteed. When using interactive methods, there are certainly problems of running out of time. For this, the availability of pedagogical skills is of great importance. If a pedagogue can create a truly inquisitive, innovative, aspiring, friendly atmosphere with students, he can solve problems during any interactive style of class. For this, an interactive lesson is organized at the level of demand, it can achieve a positive result. Today, great attention is being paid to the economy and improvement of education, teacher-learner relations, techniques and technologies, organization of education based on interactive methods, and improvement of educational efficiency. The use of interactive methods in the educational system, in the educational process, is an innovative method that increases the effectiveness of education.

In conclusion, as a result of the use of innovative technologies in the field of education, during the last year, students will be able to demonstrate their abilities and opportunities, acquire the skills to work in a team, and learn to respect the opinions of others. This increases the effectiveness of education and serves to guarantee the quality of education.

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